

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**IN-SILICO AND IN-VITRO PHARMACOLOGICAL
EVALUATION OF SULFAMETHOPYRAZINE AS ANTI-
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Centre, Parassala, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala**Abstract:**

Background Of The Study: The present study aim to evaluate the Anti-diabetic property of Sulfamethopyrazine using in-silico, in-vitro, Swiss ADME and Antioxidant evaluation.

Methods: The data of Sulfamethopyrazine was collected from pubmed, pubchem, google scholar. By using software's such as pyrex and pymol, Sulfamethopyrazine was docked with Antidiabetic receptors 3OLI and 4W93. The drug was brought from Chennai in the month of April. Then in-vitro studies were performed by using Glucose uptake assay and Inhibition of endogenous glucose production methods. Antioxidant evaluation was carried out by using DPPH method. Pharmacokinetic evaluation was done by using Swiss ADME Software.

Keywords: Anti-diabetic property, Sulfamethopyrazine, Docking , In-silico Method, In-vitro Method, Swiss ADME, Antioxidant evaluation, DPPH radical scavenging assay method.

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Please cite this article in press Saranya T.J et al., In-Silico And In-Vitro Pharmacological Evaluation Of Sulfamethopyrazine As Anti-Diabetic Agent., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12(04).

INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus is a heterogeneous group of disorders characterized by hyperglycaemia due to an absolute or relative deficit in insulin production or action. The chronic hyperglycaemia of diabetes mellitus is associated with end organ damage, dysfunction, and failure of retina, kidney, nervous system, heart, and blood vessels.^[1,2]

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is commonest endocrine disorder that affects more than 100 million people worldwide (6% population). It is caused by deficiency or ineffective production of insulin by pancreas which results in increase or decrease in concentrations of glucose in the blood.^[3]

The presence of DM shows increased risk of many complications such as cardiovascular diseases, peripheral vascular diseases, stroke, neuropathy, renal failure, retinopathy, blindness, amputations etc.^[4,5]

Drugs are used primarily to save life and alleviate symptoms. Secondary aims are to prevent long term diabetic complications and by eliminating various risk factors, to increase longevity. Insulin replacement therapy is the mainstay for patients with type 1 DM while diet and lifestyle modifications are considered the corner stone for the treatment and management of type 2 DM.^[6]

TYPES:

❖ Type 1 diabetes mellitus (insulin dependent diabetes mellitus -IDDM) ❖ Type 2 diabetes mellitus (non-insulin dependent diabetes mellitus)

Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus:

Type I diabetes is an autoimmune disease characterized by a local inflammatory reaction in and

around islets that is followed by selective destruction of insulin secreting cells. This type of diabetes is additionally known as reaction diabetes and also referred to as juvenile-onset or ketosisprone polygenic disease.^[7]

Type I diabetes, or juvenile-onset diabetes (T1DM) is a chronic disease characterized by hyperglycaemia secondary to inadequate production of insulin by the pancreas. The classic clinical presentation of T1DM is an acute onset of symptoms caused by β -cell failure. The typical symptom triad is weight loss, polyuria and polydipsia.

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus:

Type 2 DM (formerly known as non-insulin dependent DM) is the most common form of DM characterized by hyperglycaemia, insulin resistance, and relative insulin deficiency.

Type 2 diabetes is a heterogeneous condition caused by both genetic and environmental factors. The management of the disease usually requires a step wise adjustment of pharmacological therapies in combination with lifestyle modifications. It is a common disease whose prevalence markedly increases with age (>10% above 65 years).

Insulin resistance often associated with obesity, and insulin secretion defects are major risk factors of type 2 DM. A progressive decrease of β cell functions leads to glucose intolerance, which is followed by type 2 diabetes.^[8]

ETIOLOGY:

Diabetes mellitus has number of reasons that are still unknown. It is now largely understood that DM is complex in nature, with hereditary and environmental factors both playing a role.^[9]

Fig 1.1: Etiology of Diabetic Mellitus

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY:**Fig 1.2: Pathophysiology of Diabetic Mellitus**

Type 1 Diabetes mellitus: The autoimmune destruction of pancreatic β -cells leads to a deficiency of insulin secretion which results in the metabolic dearrangements associated with type 1 DM. In addition to loss of insulin secretion, the function of pancreatic α -cells is also abnormal and there is excessive secretion of glucagon in type 1 DM patients. The inappropriately elevated glucagon levels exacerbate the metabolic defects due to insulin deficiency. All though insulin deficiency is the primary defect in type 1 DM. Deficiency in insulin leads to uncontrolled lipolysis and elevated levels of free fatty acids in the plasma, which suppresses glucose metabolism in peripheral tissues such as skeletal muscle.

Type 2 Diabetes mellitus: Type 2 DM is a heterogeneous disorder characterized by the presence of both insulin resistance and relative insulin deficiency or β -cell deficiency. Insulin resistance manifests by an increase in lipolysis and free fatty acid production, increase in hepatic glucose production and decrease in skeletal muscle uptake of glucose. Free fatty acids indirectly lead to hyperglycemia by stimulating hepatic glucose production. β -cell dysfunction is progressive and contributes to

worsening blood glucose control with time.

Type 2 DM occurs when a diabetogenic lifestyle (excessive calories, inadequate caloric expenditure and obesity) is superimposed upon a susceptible genotype. Weight gain associated with significant insulin resistance appears to vary between racial and ethnic groups. Overweight patients from the Indian subcontinent are mildly overweight by Western standards but may be very insulin resistant. The high prevalence of type 2 DM in Native American population is usually associated with marked obesity.^[10]

SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS

- ❖ Blurry vision
- ❖ Feeling hungry
- ❖ Numbness in hands or feet
- ❖ Feeling tired
- ❖ Unplanned weight loss ❖ Frequent urination

CLASSIFICATION OF ANTI-DIABETIC AGENTS**1. Sulfonylureas**

- First generation: Tolbutamide

- Second generation: Glibenclamide, Glipizide

2. Meglitinide analogues

- Repaglinide, Nateglinides

3. Glucagon-like peptide (GLP-1) receptor agonist

- Exenatide, Liraglutide

4. Dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitors

- Sitagliptin, Vildagliptin

SULFONYLUREAS

Mechanism of action: Sulfonylureas act by activating beta cell sulfonylurea receptor 1 (SUR1) leading to closure of ATP dependent potassium channels. Thus, the potassium flow across plasma membrane is stopped leading to depolarisation, which opens voltage sensitive calcium channels. Consequently, there is an uptake of extra cellular calcium, activating a cytoskeletal system, which causes translocation of secretory granules to the cell surface and extrusion of insulin through exocytosis. Exocytosis results in the fusion of the secretory granules with the plasma membrane leading to the release of insulin into the extracellular space to reach the capillary blood flow. Hence, sulfonylureas administration must be carefully monitor since it can lead to hypoglycemia, weight gain and hyperinsulinemia.

MEGLITINIDE ANALOGUES

Mechanism of action: Meglitinides are insulin secretagogues with a similar mechanism of action to sulfonylureas, acting on ATP-dependent potassium channels. Therefore, they fail to have any effect in patients who have already been treated with maximal therapeutic dosage of sulfonylureas.

GLUCAGON-LIKE PEPTIDE (GLP-1) RECEPTOR AGONIST

Mechanism of action: GLP-1 exerts direct effects in several organs, due to interaction with its receptor located in organs such as pancreas, brain, heart, lung, stomach, intestine, and kidney. On pancreatic-cells, this interaction leads to activation of adenylate cyclase and production of cAMP that mediates its stimulatory effect on insulin secretion via protein kinase A. However, GLP-1 stimulates insulin secretion via several other mechanisms, including a direct inhibition of ATP dependent potassium channels. As sulfonylureas, this leads to an increase in intracellular levels of calcium and a rise in mitochondrial ATP synthesis which leads to a further membrane depolarization. Finally, it causes insulin granule exocytosis from pancreatic-cell.

DIPEPTIDYL PEPTIDASE-4(DPP-4) INHIBITORS

Mechanism of action: DPP-4 inhibitors competitively and reversibly inhibit DPP-4 providing

up to 90% inhibition of its activity during a 24-hour period. Therefore, DPP-4 inhibitors promote insulin secretion and inhibit glucagon secretion, being these actions dependent on the presence of glucose.^[11]

SULFAMETHOPYRAZINE

The anti-diabetes property of Sulfamethopyrazine was evaluated by using *In-silico*, *In-vitro*, Swiss ADME and Antioxidant evaluation in this study.

Sulfamethopyrazine is an antibiotic, used to treat chronic respiratory problems such as chronic bronchitis. It can also be administered for the treatment of urinary tract infection, malaria. The main mechanism of its action is to inhibit the growth and thereby kill disease-causing parasites. Sufficient precautions must be taken if you are pregnant or breastfeeding as the medicine may cause complications in foetal health or in infants.

IN-SILICO METHOD

The interaction between the ligand and protein was determined by using Auto dock via Pyrex virtual screening tool. Docking studies were conducted to determine the interactions and principles of bonding between proteins and ligands.

- Docking methodology aims to predict the experimental binding modes and affinities of small molecules within the binding site of particular receptor targets.
- Used as a standard computational tool in drug design for lead compound optimisation and in virtual screening studies to find novel biologically active molecules.
- Basic tools of a docking methodology include a search algorithm and an energy scoring function for generating and evaluating ligand poses.
- They increase the chance of success in many stages of the discovery process.
- They facilitate accessing huge amount of data generated.^[12]

ANTI -OXIDANT STUDY

The main characteristic of an antioxidant is its ability to trap free radicals. Oxidative metabolism is essential for the survival of cells. A side effect of this dependence is the production of free radicals and other reactive oxygen species that cause oxidative changes. Defence mechanisms against the effects of excessive oxidations are provided by the action of various antioxidants and the need to measure antioxidant activity is well documented.

DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay

The radical scavenging activity of different extracts was determined by using DPPH assay. The decrease in the absorption of the DPPH solution after the addition

of an antioxidant was measured at 517 nm. Ascorbic acid (10mg/ml DMSO) was used as reference. ^[15]

IN-VITRO STUDY

1. Determination of *in-vitro* glucose uptake assay on cultured 16 cell lines: The Glucose Uptake-Glo™ Assay is a nonradioactive, plate-based, homogeneous bioluminescent method for measuring glucose uptake in mammalian cells based on the detection of 2-deoxyglucose 6-phosphate (2DG6P). When 2-deoxyglucose (2DG) is added to cells, it is transported across the membrane and rapidly phosphorylated in the same manner as glucose. ^[13]

2. Endogenous inhibition of glucose production in liver: The liver plays a major role in maintaining normal whole body glucose levels by regulating the processes of *de novo* glucose production (gluconeogenesis) and glycogen breakdown (glycogenolysis), thus controlling the levels of hepatic glucose release. Maintaining the blood glucose concentration through an intricate balance between glucose uptake and endogenous glucose production is used to maintain constant glucose concentrations. ^[14]

PHARMACOKINETIC STUDY

Pharmacokinetic evaluation such as absorption, distribution, metabolism, elimination was carried out by using different kind of software. The evaluation of pharmacokinetic properties helps to reduce failures during the drug development process.

Swiss ADME

Swiss ADME is a free web tool to evaluate pharmacokinetic, drug likeness and medical chemistry friendliness of medical molecules. Swiss ADME web tool that gives free access to a pool of fast yet robust predictive models for physicochemical properties, pharmacokinetics, drug likeness and medical chemistry friendliness, among which in-house proficient methods such as the BOILED Egg, ILOGP and Bioavailability Radar. ^[16]

AIM

The aim of this study was to determine the anti-diabetic property of Sulfamethopyrazine using *in silico*, *in-vitro*, Swiss ADME and antioxidant evaluation.

OBJECTIVES

- *In-silico* evaluation of Sulfamethopyrazine on anti-diabetic receptor (3OLI, 4W93).
- Pharmacokinetic evaluation of Sulfamethopyrazine by using Swiss ADME software.
- *In-vitro* anti-oxidant evaluation of Sulfamethopyrazine by DPPH.
- *In-vitro* anti-diabetic evaluation of Sulfamethopyrazine by Glucose uptake assay and

inhibition of endogenous glucose production.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The data of Sulfamethopyrazine was collected from pubmed, pubchem, google scholar. By using software's such as pyrex and pymol. Sulfamethopyrazine was docked with anti-diabetic receptors (3OLI, 4W93). The drug was brought from Chennai in the month of April. Then *in-vitro* studies were performed by using Glucose uptake assay and Inhibition of endogenous glucose production methods. Antioxidant evaluation was carried out by using DPPH method. Pharmacokinetic evaluation was done by using Swiss ADME Software.

SULFAMETHOPYRAZINE

Sulfamethopyrazine is a long-acting sulphonamides antibacterial. Sulfamethopyrazine contain Pyridazine ring (6memebered ring with adjacent 2 nitrogen) In the Pyridazine ring at 3rd position a methoxy group (oxygen with methyl group) and at 6th position there is a sulphonamide bond connected with aniline (benzene ring with amino group) ^[4]

These are ultralong acting compounds, action lasting >1 week because of high plasma protein binding and slow renal excretion ($t^{1/2}$ 5-9 days). They attain low plasma concentration (of free form) and are not suitable for treatment of acute pyrogenic infections, but are used in combination with pyrimethazine in treatment of malaria, *Pneumocystis jiroveci* pneumonia in AIDS patients and in toxoplasmosis. Because they have caused serious cutaneous reactions, large scale use of the combination for prophylaxis of malaria is not recommended. ^[5]

ANTIDIABETIC RECEPTORS

Docking studies were conducted to determine the interactions and principles of bonding between receptors and ligands. Sulfamethopyrazine is used as the ligand and the two receptors are used in this study are 3OLI & 4W93.

❖ 3OLI

Fig 4.1: 3OLI Diabetic receptor

Structure of human pancreatic alpha-amylase in complex with acarviosin IV03

- Human pancreatic alpha- amylase in complex with montbretin A
- Classification: HYDROLASE/HYDROLASE INHIBITOR
- Organism(s): Homo sapiens
- Expression System: Saccharomyces cerevisiae.

❖ 4W93

Fig 4.2: 4W93 Diabetic receptor

- Human pancreatic alpha- amylase in complex with montbretin A
- Classification: HYDROLASE/HYDROLASE INHIBITOR.
- Organism(s): Homo sapiens.
- Expression System: Komagataella pastoris.

METHODS**IN-SILICOSTUDIES**

In-silico computer simulation studies and docking studies are proved to be the best tool used to investigate the complementary and level of interaction at the molecular level between the compounds of natural or synthetic origin and a potential target. The drug likeness scores were evaluated by computational method using Swiss ADME software.

Drawing Software

The structure of the compound was drawn in NOVO PRO LABS. It is chemically intelligent drawing software useful to draw chemical structures of almost all compounds including organics and polymers.

Procedure

- Take NOVO PRO LABS on the browser and convert 2D smile to 3D structure.
- Then paste canonical smile on the input smile.
- Click on the submit button.
- Then download the 3D model.

Steps involved in the docking study of the lead compounds

Docking study of the lead molecules were performed using Auto docking Program in PyRx software. The binding affinity of the lead compound and 3oLI, 4W93 are determined.

Step 1: Ligand preparation

The chemical structure of the compound was obtained from freely accessible chemistry data base, Pubchem. The chemical structure of the compound was downloaded into 3D format.

Step 2: Selection of receptors

Target receptor such as 3OLI and 4W93 were selected RCSB Pdb homepage from google chrome. The receptor is downloaded and after processing it was converted into input format.

Step 3: Receptor processing

Receptor structure processing includes removal of hydrogen, water molecules and small molecule if any.

Step 4: Docking analysis

Docking analysis was done by auto dock program in PyRx software. For this installed Auto dock tools and PyRx. ^[12]

Procedure

- Opened PyRx →File →Load molecule →Open receptor and ligand in PyRx window.
- Right click on ligand →Auto dock →Make ligand
- Right click on receptor →Auto dock →Make macro molecule
- Start →Forward → Maximise → Forward

Step 5: Visualization

• File →Open →This PC →Local disc→ Users→ mgl tool→ PyRx→ Ligand →Open

• File →Open →This PC →Local disc→ Users→ mgl tool→ PyRx→ Macro molecule → Open

ANTI-OXIDANT STUDY

The main characteristic of an antioxidant is its ability to trap free radicals. Oxidative metabolism is essential for the survival of cells. A side effect of this dependence is the production of free radicals and other reactive oxygen species that cause oxidative changes. Defence mechanisms against the effects of excessive oxidations are provided by the action of various antioxidants and the need to measure antioxidant activity is well documented. [6] **Principle**

1, 1-diphenyl-2-picryl hydrazyl is a stable free radical with pink colour which turns yellow when scavenged. The DPPH assay uses this character to show free radical scavenging activity. The scavenging reaction between (DPPH) and an antioxidant (H-A) can be written as, $DPPH + [H-A] \rightarrow DPPH-H + (A)$ Antioxidants react with DPPH and reduce it to DPPH-H and as consequence the absorbance decreases. The degree of discoloration indicates the scavenging potential of the antioxidant compounds or extracts in terms of hydrogen donating ability.

Reagent preparation

0.1mM DPPH solution was prepared by dissolving 4mg of DPPH in 100ml of methanol.

Procedure

Different concentrations of sample such as 12.5µg/ml-200µg/ml from stock solution were made up to a volume of 20µl with DMSO and 1.48ml DPPH (0.1mM) solution was added. A control without the test compound and an equivalent amount of distilled water was taken. The reaction mixture incubated in dark condition at room temperature for 20 minutes. After 20 minutes, the absorbance of the mixture was read at 517nm. 3ml of DPPH was taken as control. [15]

IN-VITRO

1. DETERMINATION OF IN-VITRO GLUCOSE UPTAKE ASSAY ON CULTURED L6 CELL LINES

- L6 (rat myoblast cell line) cells were initially procured from National Centre for Cell Sciences (NCCS), Pune, India and maintained Dulbecco's modified Eagles medium, DMEM (Sigma Aldrich, USA).
- The cell line was cultured in 25 cm²tissue culture flask with DMEM supplemented with 10% FBS, L-glutamine, sodium bicarbonate (Merck, Germany) and antibiotic solution containing: Penicillin (100U/ml), Streptomycin (100µg/ml), and Amphotericin B (2.5µg/ml). Cultured cell lines were kept at 37°C in a humidified 5% CO₂ incubator (NBS Eppendorf, Germany).

Procedure

The cells were trypsinized (500µl of 0.025% Trypsin in PBS/ 0.5mM EDTA solution) for 2 minutes and passaged to T flasks in complete aseptic conditions.

The cells were then sub cultured to a 24 well plate. After attaining 80% confluency cells were kept in DMEM without glucose for 24 hours. Standard (Metformin) and samples were added to grown cells at a final concentration of 25µg/ml, 50µg/ml and 100µg/ml from a stock solution of 1mg/ml and incubated for 24 hours in DMEM containing 300mM glucose. An untreated control with high glucose was also maintained. After incubation cells were isolated by spinning at 6000 rpm for 10 minutes. Supernatant was discarded and 200µl of cell lysis buffer (1MTris Hcl, 0.25M EDTA, 2M NaCl, 0.5% Triton) was added. The incubation was done for 30 minutes at 4°C and the glucose uptake was estimated using high sensitivity glucose oxidase kit method. All experiments were repeated in triplicates and mean average was used for calculations. [12,13]

2. ENDOGENOUS INHIBITION OF GLUCOSE PRODUCTION IN LIVER

HepG2 (Liver Hepatic Cells) cells were purchased from NCCS Pune and was maintained in Dulbecco's modified eagles' media (Sigma Aldrich) supplemented with 10% FBS and grown to confluency at 37°C in 5 % CO₂ in a humidified atmosphere in a CO₂ incubator (NBS, Eppendorf) The cells were trypsinized (500µl of 0.025% Trypsin in PBS/ 0.5mM EDTA solution (Gibco, In-vitrogen) for 2 minutes and passed to T flasks in complete aseptic conditions. The cells were then sub cultured to a 24 well plate.

Procedure

After attaining 80% confluency cells were kept in DMEM without glucose with standard (Metformin) and sample at a final concentration of 25µg/ml, 50µg/ml and 100µg/ml from a stock solution of 1mg/ml for 30 minutes and incubated for 6 hours after treating with 100nM glucagon. An untreated control without glucose was also maintained. After incubation cells were isolated by spinning at 6000 rpm for 10 minutes. Supernatant was discarded and 200µl of cell lysis buffer (1MTris Hcl, 0.25M EDTA, 2M NaCl, 0.5% Triton) was added. The incubation was done for 30 minutes at 4°C and the glucose content was estimated using glucose kit method (Erba Mannheim, Germany) and the absorbance was read at 505nm (Agilent, USA) [12,14]

PHARMACOKINETIC EVALUATION

Pharmacokinetics is the quantitative study of drug movement in, through and out of the body. The intensity of response is related to concentration of the drug at the site of action, which in turn is dependent on its pharmacokinetic properties. Pharmacokinetic evaluation such as absorption, distribution, metabolism, elimination was carried out by using different kind of software. The evaluation of

pharmacokinetic properties helps to reduce failures during the drug development process. Pharmacokinetic evaluation was evaluated by using Swiss ADME. [16]

Procedure

- Drug's canonical smile is copied from Pubchem.
- Open Swiss ADME Software and paste canonical smile and click the run button.

RESULTS:

❖ *IN-SILICO* STUDY

✓ *In-silico* method of evaluation is carried out by using Auto dock via Pyrex virtual screening tool. Sulfamethopyrazine is used as the ligand and 3OLI as the receptors. Sulfamethopyrazine show more affinity (-7.0 to -6.4) towards 3OLI than the other receptors it also shows 9 hydrogen bonding with receptors. Affinity of Sulfamethopyrazine with 3OLI receptor in shown Table No.5.1.

✓ *In-silico* method of evaluation is carried out by using Auto dock via Pyrex virtual screening tool. Sulfamethopyrazine is used as the ligand and 4W93 as the receptors. Sulfamethopyrazine show more affinity (-6.7 to -5.2) towards 4W93 than the other receptors it also shows 9 hydrogen bonding with receptors. Affinity of Sulfamethopyrazine with 4W93 receptor in shown Table No.5.2.

Molecular docking images

Fig 5.1: Image of 3OLI with Sulfamethopyrazine

Fig 5.2: Image of 4W93 with Sulfamethopyrazine

❖ ANTI-OXIDANT STUDY

Anti-oxidant study is carried out by DPPH radical scavenging assay method. The obtained during this study is represented by a graph. It contains concentration of sample on x-axis and percentage of inhibition on y-axis which shows that percentage of inhibition increases with increasing concentration of sample. Percentage of inhibition of anti-oxidant study in Sulfamethopyrazine is shown in Table N0.5.3.

Calculation

$$\text{Percentage of inhibition} = \frac{\text{control} - \text{test}}{\text{control}} \times 100$$

Fig 5.3: Graphical representation depicting the DPPH activity of Sulfamethopyrazine, the percentage of inhibition increases with concentration of sample. Along Y axis Percentage inhibition, Along X axis varied concentration of Sulfamethopyrazine

❖ *IN-VITRO***1. Determination of *in-vitro* glucose uptake assay on cultured L6 cell lines**

Determination of *in-vitro* glucose uptake assay cultured L6 cell line method result is represented by plotting two graphs, concentration of sample on x-axis and glucose level on y-axis and, concentration of sample on x-axis and percentage of glucose uptake on y-axis. It indicates that as the glucose uptake increases with increasing concentration of drug. The percentage glucose uptake assay is shown Table No.5.4.

Calculation

$$\text{Total Glucose in mg/dl} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of Test}}{\text{Absorbance of Standard}} \times 100$$

$$\% \text{ Glucose uptake} = \frac{\text{OD of Test} - \text{OD of Control}}{\text{OD of Test}} \times 100$$

Average OD of Standard = 0.497

Fig 5.4: Graphical representation depicting the glucose level of sample increases with concentration of sample when compare to control group. Along Y axis glucose level, Along X axis varied concentration of sample.

Percentage glucose uptake

Fig 5.5: Graphical representation depicting the percentage glucose uptake of sample increases with concentration of sample. Along Y axis percentage glucose uptake, Along X axis varied concentration of sample

2. Endogenous inhibition of glucose production in liver

Endogenous inhibition of glucose production in liver study result is represented graphically by concentration of sample on x-axis and glucose level on y-axis which shows that the percentage of inhibition increases with increase in concentration of sample. Percentage inhibition of glucose production is shown in Table No.5.5.

CALCULATIONS

Total Glucose in mg/dl = Absorbance of Test X 100

Absorbance of Standard

% Inhibition = $\frac{\text{Amount of glucose in control} - \text{amount of glucose in Test X}}{\text{Amount of glucose in control}} \times 100$

Average OD of Standard = 0.4909

Fig 5.6: Graphical representation depicting the glucose level of sample. Along Y axis glucose level, Along X axis varied concentration of sample.

Percentage inhibition

Fig 5.7: Graphical representation depicting the percentage inhibition of sample increases with concentration of sample. Along Y axis percentage glucose uptake, Along X axis varied concentration of sample.

❖ PHARMACOKINETIC EVALUATION

Pharmacokinetic evaluation is carried out by using Swiss ADME Software which evaluates the water solubility and other pharmacokinetic properties like GI absorption, BBB permeant. Pharmacokinetic evaluation of glucose is shown in Table No.5.6.

Fig 5.8: Pharmacokinetic evaluation of Sulfamethopyrazine

Water solubility

Log s (ESOL) : -2.22

Solubility : 1.68+00 mg/ml;5.99e-03mol/l

Class : soluble

Log S (Ali) : -2.70

Solubility: 5.53e-01mg/ml;1.97e-03mol/l

Class : Soluble

Log S (SILICOS-IT) : -3.91

Solubility : 3.42e-02mg/ml;1.22e-04mol/l

Class : soluble

Pharmacokinetics

GI absorption : High

BBB permeant : No P-gp substrate: No CYP1A2

Inhibitor : No CYP2C19 Inhibitor: No CYP2C9

Inhibitor : No CYP2D6 : No CYP3A4 : No

DISCUSSION:

Diabetes mellitus is a heterogeneous group of disorders characterized by hyperglycaemia due to an absolute or relative deficit in insulin production or action. The chronic hyperglycemia of diabetes mellitus is associated with end organ damage,

dysfunction, and failure, including the retina, kidney, nervous system, heart, and blood vessels. These are mainly 2 type of Diabetic mellitus, which are Type 1 Diabetic mellitus (Insulin depended Diabetes mellitus) and Type -2 (non-insulin depended Diabetes mellitus).

Type I diabetes is an autoimmune disease characterized by a local inflammatory reaction in and around islets that is followed by selective destruction of insulin secreting cells. This type of diabetes is additionally known as reaction diabetes and referred to as juvenile-onset or ketosis prone polygenic disease.

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In-silico method of evaluation is carried out by using Auto dock via Pyrex virtual screening tool. Docking studies were conducted to determine the interactions and principles of bonding between proteins and ligands. Sulfamethopyrazine is used as the ligand and

3OLI and 4W93 as the receptors. Sulfamethopyrazine show more affinity towards 3OLI and 4W93 than the other receptors it also shows hydrogen bonding with receptors.

Sulfamethopyrazine is used to treat chronic respiratory problems such as chronic bronchitis. It may also be administered for the use of urinary tract infection, malaria. The main mechanism of its action is to inhibit the growth and thereby kill disease-causing parasites. Sulfamethopyrazine contain Pyridazine ring (6-membered ring with 2 adjacent nitrogen atoms). In the Pyridazine ring at 3rd position a methoxy group (oxygen with methyl group) and at 6th position there is a sulphonamides bond connected with aniline (benzene ring with amino group).

In-vitro method of evaluation conducted by using two methods which are determination *in-vitro* glucose uptake assay on cultured L6 cell lines and endogenous inhibition of glucose production in liver. The result obtained during this study is represented by plotting a

graph it indicates that as the glucose uptake increases with increasing concentration of drug, in determination of *in-vitro* glucose uptake assay cultured L6 cell line method and the percentage of inhibition increases with increase in concentration of sample in endogenous inhibition of glucose production in liver. The main characteristics of an anti-oxidant are its ability to trap free radicals.

Anti-oxidant study is carried out by DPPH radical scavenging assay method. In this study, percentage of inhibition increases with increasing concentration of sample. From all these results the drug Sulfamethopyrazine have anti-diabetic activity. The main characteristic of an antioxidant is its ability to trap free radicals. Oxidative metabolism is essential for the survival of cells. A side effect of this dependence is the production of free radicals and other reactive oxygen species that cause oxidative changes.

SUMMARY

Diabetes mellitus is a heterogeneous group of disorders characterized by hyperglycaemia due to an absolute or relative deficit in insulin production or action. Sulfamethopyrazine is an antibiotic and its Anti-diabetes activity is evaluated by *in-silico*, *in-vitro* methods. *In-vitro* method of evaluation conducted by using two methods which are determination *in-vitro* glucose uptake assay on cultured L6 cell lines and endogenous inhibition of glucose production in liver. Anti-oxidant study is carried out by DPPH radical scavenging assay method. Pharmacokinetic evaluation is carried out by using Swiss ADME Software.

Sulfamethopyrazine is used as the ligand and 3OLI and 4W93 as the receptors for *in-silico* study. *In-silico* method of evaluation is carried out by using Auto dock via Pyrex virtual screening tool. Sulfamethopyrazine show more affinity towards 3OLI (-7.0 to -6.4) and 4W93 (-6.7 to -5.2) than the other receptors and it also shows hydrogen bonding with receptors.

Determination of *in-vitro* glucose uptake assay cultured L6 cell line method result is represented by plotting two graphs. It indicates that as the glucose uptake increases with increasing concentration of drug. Endogenous inhibition of glucose production in liver study result is represented graphically which shows that the percentage of inhibition increases with increase in concentration of sample.

Anti-oxidant study is carried out by DPPH radical scavenging assay method. The obtained during this study is represented by a graph which shows that percentage of inhibition increases with increasing concentration of sample.

Pharmacokinetic evaluation is carried out by using Swiss ADME Software. Water solubility and other pharmacokinetic properties like GI absorption, BBB permeant are evaluated.

CONCLUSIONS:

Sulfamethopyrazine is an antibiotic and its anti-diabetic activity is evaluated by *in-silico*, *in-vitro* methods. Sulfamethopyrazine show more affinity towards 3OLI and 4W93 than the other receptors in *in-silico* methods and it also shows hydrogen bonding with receptors.

The result obtained during this *in-vitro* study is represented by plotting a graph it indicates that as the glucose uptake increases with increasing concentration of drug, in determination of *in vitro* glucose uptake assay cultured L6 cell line method and the percentage of inhibition increases with increase in concentration of sample in endogenous inhibition of glucose production in liver.

Anti-oxidant study is carried out by DPPH radical scavenging assay method, percentage of inhibition increases with increasing concentration of sample. Pharmacokinetic evaluation is carried out by using Swiss ADME Software. Water solubility and other pharmacokinetic properties like GI absorption, BBB permeant are evaluated. From all these results the drug Sulfamethopyrazine have anti-diabetic activity.

FUTURE WORK

Further studies are required to prove that the compound is used as an anti-diabetic activity. It

required demonstrating the *in-vivo* methods. Furthermore, studies are recommended to find its efficacy and safety in long term anti-diabetic therapy.

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